

EARTH SCIENCES

THE FEATURES OF THE TOURIST SEASON 2022 AND THE PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UKRAINE

Kovalska L.,

candidate of geographical sciences,

Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian national university,

associate professor of the department of tourism and regional studies,

Ivano-Frankivsk

Shchuka H.,

professor of the department of geography and tourism, doctor of pedagogical sciences, head of the educational laboratory of the tourist information center «Rakotsi-Tours»,

Transcarpathian hungarian institution named after Ferenc Rakoci II

Mikhailuk A.

graduate student of the department of socio-economic geography, faculty of geography, Ivan Franko National university of Lviv

Abstract

The article analyzes the current state of tourism development in Ukraine, particularly during wartime and post-war periods. The article aims to outline the features of the development of the national tourism industry during war, taking into account the European integration process and internal organizational and managerial decisions and to present the prospects and trends of the industry's development in the post-war period. The research methods used include statistics, analysis, synthesis, comparison, interpretation, and forecasting. The results. The study discusses the fluctuating state of the tourism business during wartime, considering both objective and subjective factors. It also analyzes data from the State statistics service of Ukraine from 2000 to 2022, highlighting the progressive development of tourism in peacetime and the regressive development during the period of full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine. The article presents the realities of the tourism business in 2022, taking into account the economic, financial, military, and demographic situations. The challenges and risks that the post-war period may bring to the development of the tourism industry are also identified. The study notes that the industry is currently adapting to societal instability and responding to various types of risks. The article identifies the main promising directions for the development of tourism in the coming years and emphasizes the importance of international agreements regarding transport logistics for its successful development. The novelty of the research lies in the fact that it characterizes for the first time the changes in national tourism during the war period, in particular, changes in the geography of tourist destinations and the transition of the industry to the information-digital era. It is determined that changes in the tourism industry of Ukraine are related to the decline in economic activity, security, and demographic situation. New promising directions in tourism are presented: military-patriotic and natural-rehabilitation. It is noted that international and domestic tourism in the post-war period may be subject to sanitary-epidemiological, ecological, and technological risks. It is predicted that the spiritual component of the Ukrainian people will serve as a tourist magnet, which will be manifested in the export of cultural and tourist heritage through its identification and development of cross-border and national tourist products. Transport logistics, thanks to agreements with carriers on «open skies» and rail connections with EU countries, will also contribute to the development of tourism.

Keywords: tourist destination, tourism in the post-war period, military-patriotic, natural-rehabilitation.

Importance and relevance of the research topic. Today Ukraine lacks a developed strategy or program for the development and organization of tourism during wartime and the post-war period, which has led and will lead to significant changes in the tourism industry. Currently, it is necessary to plan a national tourism business based on the experience of countries that have experienced wartime aggression, as well as an objective assessment of current realities. Therefore, an analysis of the development of the tourism business during the wartime period, as well as the identification of new tourism directions, prospects for the development of tourist destinations, potential consumer groups of tourist products after its completion, is timely and has led to the relevance of the chosen topic.

The current state of the researched issue. The collapse caused by the massive invasion of Russian forces into Ukraine has led to significant changes in the country as a whole, including the economy and consequently, in the national and international tourism industry. The focus on the state of this industry is due to the significant gap between its level of development before and during the war. One of the notable drivers for research in this context has been the rapid reorientation of tourist flows, changes in countries and regions that are donors of tourists, and the formation of new types and directions of tourism. The basis for recovery has been the experience of restoring the tourism industry in countries such as Slovenia, Croatia, Egypt, etc. One of the main key positions for the restoration of the national tourism business has been the need to fill the state and local budgets. Special attention has also been given to

changes in the socio-cultural environment and the export of cultural heritage.

The article aims to outline the features of the development of the national tourism industry during war, taking into account the European integration process and internal organizational and managerial decisions and to present the prospects and trends of the industry's development in the post-war period. It also presents directions and ways of tourism development, as well as highlighting the priority tourist destinations as a condition for the development of infrastructure-sustaining regions, which will contribute to the development of territorial communities.

The analysis of the features of tourism development and the experience of countries that have experienced wartime and restored domestic and international tourism were borrowed from works of both foreign and ukrainian scientists. For example, David Currie's work [1] occupies a significant place in the world scientific heritage. The work of Dedylova T., Nosyryev O., and Osipova S. [2] is dedicated to the development of conceptual principles for the restoration of Ukraine's tourism potential in the post-war period from 2022-2030 based on strategic management. N. Barvinok studied and justified war tourism as an important factor in tourism development in Ukraine during the post-war period and identified the tourist resources that will serve as the basis for its organization [3]. L. Bozhko and V. Kholodok studied the impact of wartime on tourism development and analyzed the experience of restoring tourism in countries affected by the armed conflict [4]. L. Kovalska's works include several publications dedicated to the aggression and annexation of Ukrainian territories by russia [5], the impact of migration processes on tourism development in Ukraine during the period of russia's aggression [6], and more. However, the reality of the tourism industry during russia's massive invasion into Ukraine in 2022 remains a white spot.

Research methods. In the analysis of the national tourist market, we used the following methods of scientific research: statistics and comparison – with a determined number of tourists served by tour operators and travel agents over a 22-year period, analysis and synthesis – with a determined state of the tourist market during the war period in Ukraine, forecasting – taking into account the experience of the countries of Georgia and Moldova, the interpretation of the devel-

opment of tourist transport logistics in Ukraine was carried out, and taking into account the objective and subjective factors that affect the development of the tourism industry, the main tourist destinations in the post-war period were indicated.

The main material. The tourist industry during the war between russia and Ukraine is in a state of stagnation. This full-scale war has defined the course of negative processes, including mass migration processes: emigration, re-emigration, forced internal displacement, as well as the decline of the economy, the manifestation of hatred towards anything russian, looting both by local residents invaders and others. All of these processes undoubtedly affect and determine social relations between people, including consumers of tourist services.

The national tourism market during the war is volatile and is influenced by both objective and subjective factors. Among the objective factors are the state of the tourist infrastructure, the qualifications of professionals in the service industry, the availability of information about tourist attractions, and so on. Subjective factors include political and economic conditions, annexation of territories, the pandemic, and so on. However, despite all these factors, the tourism industry in Ukraine is still functioning.

To determine the real state of the national tourism market, we will analyze it before the annexation of ukrainian territories by russia, during the pandemic, and during the mass military invasion of russians into ukrainian lands. Analyzing State Statistics data from 2000 to 2022, it was determined that the boom of tourists served by tour operators and travel agents (by types of tourism) fell on 2019 (excluding the temporarily occupied territory of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, Sevastopol, and temporarily occupied territories in Donetsk and Luhansk regions) and amounted to 6,132,097 people (fig. 1). Of these, outbound tourists accounted for 5,524,866 people, domestic tourists 520,391 people, inbound (foreign) tourists – 86,840 people.

According to the Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine, the peak of inbound (foreign) tourists was observed in 2003 and amounted to 590,641 people out of a total of 2,856,983 people served by tour operators and travel agents (by types of tourism). Of these, 344,332 were outbound tourists and 1,922,010 were domestic tourists [7].

Fig. 1. Number of tourists in Ukraine served by tour operators and travel agents, by types of tourism.

Since 2014, the number of foreign tourists has sharply decreased due to Ukraine's image as a country at war. Since 2016, the flow of international tourists, including outbound tourists, has increased due to the visa-free regime with EU countries. This process was also facilitated by equal prices for tourist products on both international and national markets. During 2020, the number of both outbound and inbound tourists, taking into account quarantine measures related to the Covid-19 pandemic, also significantly decreased.

The realities of the tourism business in 2022 also turned out to be unpromising, particularly in terms of infrastructure (destruction and failure of tourist service establishments and facilities), financial (reduction of wages, inflation of the hryvnia, increase in the exchange rate of currencies, bankruptcy of tourist firms), military (full-scale hostilities of Russia in tourist destinations, for example, along the Black and Azov Seas coasts), and demographic (reduction in the number of potential consumers of tourist services, orientation of services to a certain age category – children's tourism, etc.) situations, which did not contribute to people traveling for recreation. However, despite such radical changes, the tourism industry replenished the state budget, albeit to a lesser extent.

According to the State Tourism Agency, 33.34% less taxes were paid to the state budget in 9 months of 2022 than in the same period in 2021. A significant decline in financial revenues was recorded in the Capital region, particularly in Kyiv – by 43 %, in the Black Sea (southern), namely in the Odesa region – by 78 %. Par-

tial cessation of revenues to the state budget was observed in the Sumy and Chernihiv regions, and complete cessation – in the Kharkiv, Luhansk, Donetsk, and Kherson regions. During 2022, the number of taxpayers also decreased by 28 % [8].

The national tourism market, during 2022, acquired a unique character, which was manifested in: the locality of its manifestation and the displacement of the geography of tourist destinations, the suspension of international inbound and partially outbound tourism, changes in the geography of tourist donor regions and the behavior of consumers and tourism sector workers, differentiation and stratification of the tourism product, and the formation of new tourism directions.

The local nature of tourism and the shift in the geography of tourist destinations. During 2022, the national tourism market in Ukraine exhibited a particular character, which was manifested in the localization of its development and the shift in the geography of tourist destinations. Despite the state of war in Ukraine, the tourism industry continued to operate in the relatively peaceful western part of the country. However, the development of tourism had a local character, primarily focused on mountainous areas and resort destinations within the Carpathian tourist destination. This shift in focus was caused by the war, which led to the occupation of most of the coastal resorts by Russia, the destruction of infrastructure in most regional centers and cities on the left bank of Ukraine, as well as in some administrative centers on the right bank, and damage to transport logistics and critical infrastructure centers across the country.

According to the State Agency for the development of tourism (DART) the tourism industry grew by almost 130% in Carpathian destinations compared to last year, namely, positive dynamics of tax collection was observed in Ivano-Frankivsk and Lviv regions [9].

The increase in such a fee is driven by the growing number of visitors, although it had varying levels throughout 2022. In the spring of 2022, within the Carpathian tourist destination, tourists self-organized in small groups, with most choosing to travel on foot. Bicycles and/or quad bikes were rarely rented from rental points. Accommodation was mainly organized in rural green estates or hotels. The prices of tourist products decreased by almost half compared to the previous year [10]. Prices also decreased in accommodation establishments, for example, at the Bukovel tourist complex, the cost of a room in a hotel with a pool was 600 UAH, and in Yaremche city – 300 UAH.

During the summer of 2022, the development of domestic tourism was activated. Using the example of the tourist company «Edelweiss» in Yaremche, Ivano-Frankivsk region, excursion services were the most popular among tourists. Excursions were mainly organized on weekends. Among the popular tourist tours were climbing mountain peaks (Mt. Sivulya, Pip-Ivan, Dovbushanka, etc.). Free introductory tours to the Carpathian living heritage sites were organized for internally displaced persons.

In the autumn and during the 2022–2023 New Year and Christmas holidays, the tourist season in the Carpathian destination resumed. For example, in the cottage town of Phoenix relax park, located in the territory of Polyanitska TG in Ivano-Frankivsk region, 500 tourists stayed at the same time. Financial receipts of the tourist town for July amounted to 6.1 millions UAH, August – 10.6 millions UAH, September – 6.4 millions UAH, October – 7.9 millions UAH, November – 4.7 millions UAH, December – 9.1 millions UAH (according to the establishment's reception data, not including revenues from other services, including food establishments). In total, over 16,000 tourists visited Phoenix relax park during this period.

Suspension of international inbound and partially outbound tourism. Safety of tourists is a priority and a guarantee for the development of international and domestic tourism. Ensuring safety, both within the Carpathian destination and during logistical transportation in a country that has declared martial law, is inappropriate. Therefore, during the war, mainly Ukrainians, who made up 95 % of tourists, and only 5 % were visitors, took part in tourism. International tourists preferred cultural and educational tourism. To achieve this goal, they chose tourist complexes such as Bukovel, Dragobrat, as well as regional centers: Lviv, Uzhhorod, Chernivtsi and Ivano-Frankivsk, and for business trips – Kyiv and Lviv.

Among outbound tourism, the backbone was made up of children, women, and people over 60 years old. According to the tourism company «Apelsin» (Ivano-Frankivsk), the main regions where requests from Ukraine for tourist services were directed in the summer season were: 75 % – Turkey, 12 % – Greece,

13 % – other countries (Spain, Bulgaria, Croatia, Montenegro), and in the winter season: Egypt – 78 %, UAE – 11 %, Dominican Republic – 8 %, other exotic countries (Mexico, Tanzania) – 3 %. In the second half of 2022, pilgrimage tours to Montenegro resumed, and children's tourism gained a new direction – to Poland, the Baltic countries, England, and so on. Overall, the number of outbound tourists decreased by almost 70 % in 2022.

Change in the geography of tourist donor regions. In the Carpathian tourist destination, prior to Russia's full-scale invasion, the capital and central regions served as donor regions for domestic tourism. Today, the guest geography consists of residents from the city of Kyiv, as well as the Kharkiv, Kherson, Mykolaiv, and Odesa regions. The geography of incoming tourists is close to foreign countries such as Moldova, Hungary, and Romania. Tourists from these countries have long-standing family relations, which also encouraged them to travel to visit their loved ones.

Change in the behavior of tourists and employees in the tourism sector. During the war, there was a change in tourist behavior, including perceptions of their surroundings and their attitudes towards themselves. These changes were driven by a noticeable convergence between consumers and employees in the tourism sector and the middle class of the information-digital era, which was shaped by the expansion of higher education, technological skills, and globalization. Representatives of this group have higher education, possess digital technologies, social networking communications, and postmodern self-expression values. Under the influence of the development of information technology, war, and the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, a new type of tourism has emerged – virtual tourism. Virtual travels contribute to the contemplation of «masterpieces of contemporary world art, raising their patriotic consciousness...». [11].

Changes in communication methods have been accompanied by an improvement in the quality of services and goods, which has facilitated the reallocation of opportunities for those employed in tourism. Promotional functions of the tourism destination are placed on them.

Differentiation and stratification of the tourist product and formation of new tourism directions. Differentiation of the tourism product in the national tourism market is carried out due to changes in the structure of population distribution, labor market, demand for professional competencies, employment and production structure. All these processes are caused by demographic collapse due to a prolonged demographic crisis (the predominance of deaths over births for almost 10 years, until 2013 and in 2022), mass emigration from Ukraine (according to the UN, the number of refugees exceeded 7.9 million people in 2022, although a significant number of them are returning), strengthening of gender imbalance (significant advantage of women over men due to irreparable losses on the front), sharp increase in mortality (particularly in the 20–35 age group) and decrease in the birth rate, depopulation of eastern and southern territories, sharp increase in the population in western and northwestern regions of

Ukraine, etc. According to the report on internal displacement in Ukraine, as of August 1, the number of officially registered persons in the Transcarpathian region was 125.8 thousand, in Lviv region – 106.6 thousand, and in Ivano-Frankivsk region – 94.9 thousand [12].

In 2022, the stratification of the tourist product in Ukraine was observed in several initiatives. The Kosiv painted ceramics were included in the Council of Europe's cultural route «European Route of Ceramics», which connects Germany, Spain, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, the UK, Turkey, and now Ukraine [13]. The project «52 Lifestyles in the Carpathians: Revival of Traditional Cultures of Work» was implemented with co-financing from the European Union [14]. In Dolyna, Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast, a tourist route to the natural monument «Kamin Kolybach» was presented as part of the project «Creating a system of comprehensive measures for tourism development in Dolyna united territorial community» [15], in Lviv, the National Museum named after Andriy Sheptytskyi hosted a virtual exhibition «Alternative Dimensions», and two new virtual museums: the «Museum of Modernism» and the «Museum of Science» were opened [16].

During the war, the formation of the tourism product was accompanied by changes in ukrainian society, namely a significant increase in identification with being ukrainian, which led to the development of patriotic tourism. There was a transformation of the tourism product towards promoting national identity, a desire to stay in Ukraine and consume ukrainian products. The development of the main types and directions of tourism, and therefore the tourism product, in the context of decentralization of power, was carried out taking into account the public opinion of the local population. Such a trend, namely, the demonstration of high civic activity of local communities and society as a whole during and in the immediate aftermath of the war, will serve as the basis for the formation and development of the tourism industry.

Today, tourism is adapting to social instability and responding to various dangers. This adaptation is reflected in the extension of logistics transportation by the InterCity train from Kyiv to Lviv, the additional launch of a new route from Zaporizhzhia to Uzhhorod via Lviv, as well as the resumption by Ukrainian railways from August 5 of the train No.55/56 «Kyiv-Yasynia (Transcarpathian region)» with stops in Yaremche, Tatariv-Bukovel, and Vorokhta [17]. Thus, the development of tourism «...depends on tourism logistics, the development of information and communication sphere...» [18].

In 2022, the most important things for most consumers of tourism services in Ukraine will be their health status, psychological comfort, interpersonal relationships, personal freedom, morality, and home comfort. Therefore, in the post-war period, considerable attention will be given to family and family values, and most consumers of tourism services will choose family vacations. Natural destinations with a focus on recreational (e.g. beach) and family vacations in nature, including ecotourism, will be preferred.

The development of medical and health tourism will also play a leading role in domestic tourism. Sanatorium and resort complexes will serve as the main facilities for physical and spiritual rehabilitation. A large portion of consumers of these services will be veterans, war children, and civilian victims in Ukraine. The development of medical and health tourism will center on the Transcarpathian, Odessa, Ivano-Frankivsk, and Volyn regions. A nature-rehabilitation direction of tourism will develop by combining medical and health tourism with ecotourism.

The Carpathian tourist destination, as the most surviving infrastructure, will restore the flow of tourists from the UAE and Kuwait. The favorable climate, hospitality of the local population, development of tourist infrastructure, and affordability of the tourist product for the middle class from Arab countries will make it possible to activate the tourist season from may to september. The main centers of rest will be tourist complexes such as «Bukovel», «Dragobrat», «Skhidnytsia», and others, as well as the city of Yaremche, the village of Tatariv, and other tourist-attractive settlements. The city of Lviv will be the center of cultural and tourist destinations, and the holding of various thematic mass events will attract the attention not only of tourists from Poland but also from other countries in Europe. The likelihood of the development of new international events and cross-border tourist routes will be significant. The development of cultural and cognitive tourism will also take place in the Kyiv and Odessa regions. The development of gastronomic tourism will flourish in Transcarpathian regions in combination with ethnic cuisines.

The recovery of Ukraine and its tourism industry, as well as its recognition in the international market, is possible through the export of ukrainian culture. With the increasing number of destroyed, damaged, or stolen cultural heritage sites in Ukraine (according to the Ministry of Culture and Information Policy of Ukraine, as of July 6, 2022, russians committed 407 crimes against ukrainian cultural heritage, and as of July 17, 2022, the number has already reached 423, totaling approximately 5–6 billion euros), there is a question of their preservation. One alternative approach is their digitization [19].

The development of international inbound tourism to Ukraine is being intensified, especially from western, northern, and central Europe. The spiritual component of the ukrainian people, including their indomitability and love for freedom, will be a tourist magnet. The military-patriotic direction of tourism will be based on these components, with the main tourist attractions being places of military glory (Chornobaivka), hero cities (Kharkiv, Mykolaiv, Chernihiv, etc.), military-historical sites such as Donetsk airport, Ilovaik (Ilovaik Cauldron), Zmiyev Fortifications (Kyiv region), Azovstal (Mariupol), and fortifications, and so on.

Taking into account the experiences of countries such as Georgia and Moldova, the increase in the number of railway routes and flights was carried out based on agreements with EU countries [20]. Similarly, the «open sky» agreements, which helped overcome aviation monopolies by increasing the number of airlines

and reducing competition on routes, should be relied upon in Ukraine's post-war period. As a result, prices for passengers have decreased, and passenger traffic at airports has increased. Other challenges in the post-war period are likely to be related to sanitary-epidemiological, ecological, and technogenic risks that will affect international and domestic tourism. Among the sanitary-epidemiological risks are the Covid-19 pandemic, the spread of epidemics such as cholera and monkeypox. Ecological risks include soil pollution, the likelihood of radiation contamination, and the destruction of biodiversity. Technogenic risks include damage and destruction of dams, which in turn will lead to the flooding of significant areas, transportation routes, and so on.

Conclusions. The Russian-Ukrainian war has caused significant changes in the development of tourism in Ukraine both «pre-war» (before 2014) and «during the war» (2022–2023). These changes were caused by both objective and subjective factors and manifested themselves in the boom of inbound international tourists in 2003 and its sharp decrease in 2022, the peak of outbound and domestic tourists in 2019 and its minimum in 2001 and 2020 respectively. During the war, the tourism industry adapted to social instability and various risks. In particular, there was a redirection of tourist flows, mainly: international outbound to Turkey, Egypt, inbound from Moldova, Belarus, Hungary, domestic from southern and eastern regions of the country to the west. The Carpathian tourist destination became the center of national tourism development. There was a change in consumer and tourism sector behavior due to their identification with the middle class of the information and digital age, as well as self-identification as «Ukrainians», and changes in communication methods, etc. As a result of the differentiation and stratification of the tourism product, Kosiv's picturesque ceramics joined the transborder tourist route «European Route of Ceramics» and a number of projects such as «52 lifestyles in the Carpathians: reviving traditional work cultures», «To the Stone of Kolibach», etc. have been implemented. There is a continuation of the implementation of new transport and logistics routes both national and international.

During the post-war period, the image and promotion of Ukraine as a tourist destination will be established on the international tourism market. The development of domestic tourism will be intensified and will present such main directions as military-patriotic and natural-rehabilitation. In the near future, the Carpathian and central-capital destinations will be the epicenters of tourism development. The main international tourist flows will be formed, including inbound tourism from Arab countries, western and central Europe, and outbound tourism directed towards friendly countries that provided assistance during the war, as well as countries with an affordable price policy for tourism products such as Egypt, Bulgaria, etc.

Research novelty. For the first time, changes in national tourism during Russia's mass military invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022 are characterized, specifically in terms of tourism destinations and the transi-

tion to the information-digital era of tourism. It is determined that changes in Ukraine's tourism industry are associated with economic stagnation, demographic situations, and institutional components in the context of decentralization of power. A forecast is made for the post-war period, including new directions in tourism: military-patriotic and natural-rehabilitation. It is noted that the spiritual component of the Ukrainian people will serve as a tourist magnet for international inbound tourists, which will be manifested in the export of cultural heritage through the identification and development of cross-border and national tourism products. Transport logistics, due to agreements with carriers on «open skies» and railway connections with EU countries, will also contribute to the development of tourism. It is noted that domestic tourism in the post-war period may be subject to sanitary-epidemiological, ecological, and technological risks.

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